

THE MAIN FEATURES OF USING MULTIMEDIA DEVICES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract:

This article reveals the integration of different types of media. It contains text, audio, video, graphics and others. Why we need to utilize different types of digital items in teaching process. The term multimedia is a term that is often heard and discussed in the field of education by technologists today. Multimedia items are used in smart classes, video projector, projection screen and so on. Multimedia plays an important role in many areas of early childhood education such as, to develop oral communication, thinking ability, understanding ability.

Key words: multimedia, educational content, technology, language learning.

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This study identifies the positive effects of different types of multimedia on primary affect. Education. Different schools in five mohlas of Alambagh were selected for investigation Area in Lucknow city. These are Pavanpuri, Kailaspuri, Gitapalli, Krishnapalli and Sujanpura. A total of 120 elementary and primary school teachers were selected for the study. Random Sampling method was used for sample selection and questionnaire table was used for data Collection. The t test used in the study to analyze the data. The results showed that there is multimedia. The ability to change the child's abilities in a positive way, to increase content-related knowledge. The word comes multimedia comes from the Latin word "multus" which means "numerous" C media which means "middle" and "centre".

Multimedia is a type of communication that uses that uses multiple forms of media. In multimedia, multiple means exchanges of information. An example of multimedia is PowerPoint used with a tape recording and photos. Multimedia improves communication by offering multiple channels through which information can be transmitted. It combines text, visual images, sound and movement to create a more immersive and engaging experience for the audience. Multimedia is rapidly evolving as a key life skill twenty-first century as the current reading. In fact, it is changing the nature of multimedia self study. Instead of limiting you to the linear presentation of printed text books, multimedia give important newness to words and make reading dynamic size. In addition to conveying meaning, words in multimedia play the role of a trigger readers can use to expand the text to learn more about the topic. This is done not only by presenting more text, but also by animating it with sound, pictures, music and video. Multimedia is rapidly evolving as a key life skill twenty-first century as the current reading. In fact, it is changing the nature of multimedia self study. Instead of limiting you to the linear presentation of printed text books, multimedia give important newness to words and make reading dynamic size. In addition to conveying meaning, words in multimedia play the role of a trigger readers can

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use to expand the text to learn more about the topic. This is done not only by presenting more text, but also by animating it with sound, pictures, music and video. Advantages of using multimedia in language learning. With the development of technology and globalization, the 21st century has become an era of bilingualism or multilingualism. Research shows that since 2000, speaking and learning English has become a necessity. And in 18 years after 2000, the graph of English speakers and learners its increasing day by day. Recently, I had the opportunity to attend a summer seminar at some universities in Uzbekistan and I was surprised to learn that many countries like ours have problems with L2 teaching. They also have pronunciation, grammatical errors, and construction problems. But many countries are using modern gadgets and are technologically advanced. They combined English teaching with technology and electronic support. They are developing and achieving good results.

There, we were introduced to many devices, applications and programs that are very useful for teaching English. English is spoken as L2 in many countries, but the use of technology has made teaching easy, convenient and accessible. The need for ICT in English language teaching:

- It is necessary to use ICT and multimedia tools to increase students' interest in the lesson. Many applications, devices and their uses engage students in learning.

- Traditional teaching always prevents students from communicating with each other. As a result, they become only passive listeners. They do not understand the structure, meaning and understanding of language, so they cannot form sentences and cannot speak. The introduction of technology allows them to improve their ability to see and communicate with visual and audio support.

- The use of ICT and multimedia enhances students' knowledge and enables them to engage in classroom learning.

- Multimedia enriches the educational content and they are many applications that offer the teacher to communicate with the students one-on-one at any time even when they are not physically present.

- Technology always comes to life in teaching. The lesson will be interesting and interactive, because ICT combines sound and image. Students can use these items in the absence of the teacher and review the content for better understanding.

- Language learning is not a one-day process. It is an ongoing process that requires 1. special attention and revision. In this way, teachers can assign assignments to students and they can view their content using devices according to their needs. Students can use technology, connect with their teachers over the Net when they are not in class, and get advice from experts when needed.

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